

Management of Common Property Resources: A Study of Deepor Beel Ramsar Site, Assam

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Abstract

Wetlands are considered the most valuable ecosystem on earth. However due to improper management and uses, often they are treated as wastelands. An attempt has been undertaken in this paper to highlight the importance of wetlands as a common property resource. Spatio-temporal study of the Deepor Beel Ramsar site has been carried out to study access to the dynamics of the wetland. The study highlights how the wetland area is shrinking and has fragmented over time owing to the rapid change in land use and land cover in the catchment area. Urbanization has not only reduced the wetland area but also resulted in degradation in terms of water quality and biodiversity; even extinction of wetlands altogether.

Keywords: Common Property Resources, Wetlands, Land use, Land cover, Geospatial technology, Ramsar site.

Introduction

Common Property Resources (CPR), also termed as Common Pool Resources in Economics, are those resources which are available for common use. Jodha (1986) defined CPR as “the resources accessible to the whole community of a village and to which no individual has exclusive property rights”. His study was concentrated on the CPR in the arid zones of India. According to him, common property resources include village meadows, public forests, wastelands, common threshing land, garages dumping grounds, watershed drainages, ponds, tanks, rivers, streams, and riverbeds, etc. Agarwal (1995) has enlisted a variety of common property resources including a variety of necessary things collected by rural families from the village forests, for domestic use and sale- fuel, food, fiber, fodder, manure, small timber, medicinal herbs, bamboo, oils, resources for house construction and handiworks, gum, resins, spices, honey, etc. The common property resources have usually been a source of economic stuff of the poor families in rural areas and have played a main resource supplement in the private-property based agriculture system. The CPRs are also a major source of biofuel for the rural people. The availability of natural resources for the common population in India can be traced back to the Indian history, the pre-British India was evident that most of the country’s natural resources were available for rural population free of cost. Generally, the natural resources were under the management of the local social groups. Gradually, these natural resources were controlled by state authorities; therefore the free accessibility to these CPR for rural poor started decreasing significantly over the period. Nevertheless, the CPRs still plays an important role in the rural economy of the local population (Report No. 452, NSS 54th Round, 1998). Arnold and Stewart (1991) have listed three major types of CPRs. These are: 1) CPR in the arid and semi-arid regions comprises nearly 20ha per village, which have been heavily degraded due to open access, 2) the hilly regions, CPR cover 60-80% of the total area under forestland, 3) in the forest areas of Central India, and CPR shares minor forest yields and timber.

Chopra and Gulati (2001) assessed that Common Property Resources covers approximately 70 MHA of land in the major states across India. Among them, forest-based CPR valued 25.069 MHA. In other words, roughly one-third of the total forest land areas are available to access and use for local people in rural areas. The remaining common natural resources are under the control of different types of local authorities and private ownership but occasionally open to common access.

Common Property Resources in India

The study on common property resources has begun during the early 1980s in India. Mostly, these studies focused on the nature and level of dependency on the CPR for rural poor. These researches deliver comprehensive information about the nature, contribution, and size of the CPRs. They also depict the problems of access to CPRs and highlight the factors responsible for degradation and exhaustion of available CPRs. The pioneering work of CPR was conducted by Jodha (1986), focuses on dry regions of Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and tropical regions of the west and southern India. He has found that common property resources comprise 15 to 23% of the total income of rural poor and contribute significantly to improve rural equity. Moreover, his work reveals that poor families are losing their accessibility to CPRs; it has been declined 26 to 52% during the mid-1950s and 1980s because of commercialization land reform. The small farmers and landless families depend on CPRs for fuelwood collection, grazing, fodder, and CPR based food consumption. Such CPRs have contributed 31-42% of the total farm input in cash. Jodha (1985, 1990) has found that the CPRs generate employment for the rural poor was higher than the public or farm works. Iyenger and Shukla (1999) have conducted a study in Gujarat villages that observed that CPRs contribute 0.1 to 11% of expenditure on farm and 1-22% 22% of non-farm families. Another study was done by Iyengar (1989; 1997) on the Gujarat villages revealed that dependency on CPRs for grazing and fuelwood was very high in the drought-prone areas. Chen (1991) has observed that the rural poor families extract more than 70% of their fuel and 55% of their fodder requirement from these CPRs a village of Ahmedabad district of Gujarat. He further observed a gradual deterioration of accessibility and increased conflict during the crisis of such resources. Pasha's (1992)'s study on three villages of Karnataka revealed that common resources contribute 10% of the total income for rural poor; there was a decline in CPRs areas by 33% within 20 years. Similarly, Back (1994) has observed CPRs have contributed 19-29% of the rural poor's income in three villages of West Bengal and conflict for accessing CPRs due to a high level of poverty.

Agarwal's (2001) study on CPRs in India revealed that more than 30 million people of India significantly depend on non-forest timber products. He also observed that the availability of common resources has decreased over the period. NSSO (1998) found that the area of CPRs varies between 1 to 32% of the geographical area across the country. Beck et al., (2001) assessed that common property resources contribute approximately US \$5 billion or 12% of the gross income of rural poor a year. Chopra (2001) has estimated the common property land and classified Indian states into three major groups: 1) states having a low share of common property land about 10% including Punjab & Haryana, 2) states sharing common property land between 10 to 30% such as Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, Orissa, Tamil Nadu, and Kerala during the early 1980s, and 3) outliers create a separate group. Dasgupta (2005) has found that 77% of lowest-income families depend on a plant of common lands in the Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh. It is 58% for high-income families. Similarly, Ghate (2005) noted that common forest land furnished 100% of fuelwood, fodder & timber in Saigata village of Maharashtra.

Problems Faced by CPR in India

Several studies related to consumption and availability of CPRs noted that they have been degraded over the period, especially during recent decades. Dasgupta (2005) has identified major four causes for such deterioration in CPRs. These reasons are 1) external circumstances like political uncertainty which affects people's property right, 2) rapid population growth which triggers resource depletion due to increased pressure on resources, 3) management practices of CPRs at the local level, and 4) social norms of behavior,

established as they are on reciprocity can be fragile. Balasubramanian and Selvaraj (2003) have found that village tank sources of irrigation have depleted over the years in the study villages of southern India due to a gradual decline in collective responsibility in their conservation because of richer families had invested in private tanks. While poor were depends on common tanks because of their extra dependency on fuel woods and fodders that grows around the tanks. Gradual exclusion of rural poor from availing the CPRs is another dark side. Several studies have revealed that the rights to CPR products are often based on private holdings; richer families availed a higher proportion of benefits, while the poor are deprived. Beteille (1983) has noted that access to CPRs in Indian society often privileged to caste-Hindus. Likewise, Agarwal and Narain (1996) have also observed a similar phenomenon in water resources management practices in the Gangetic plain of India.

Wetlands as Common Property Resources

Wetlands are the most productive and frequently highly ignored among all kinds of CPRs. It can be defined as intermediate areas between land and water resources. Wetlands considered as the “kidneys” of the landscape which cleans nutrients and sediments from land water. Usually, wetlands are referred to as "biological supermarkets" since they support all forms of life through widespread biodiversity and food webs (Mitsch and Gosselink, 1986). Generally, wetlands support to regulate water levels in a particular watershed, improve the quality of water, reduce storm damages and flood, offer habitat for wildlife and fish, assist fishing, hunting, and other leisure activities and play important functions in balancing ecological conservation. Moreover, wetlands help in significant ecological processes such as the flow of water into revisers and seas; decomposition of organic matter; release of carbon, sulfur, and nitrogen into the atmosphere; the filter of sediment, organic matter, and nutrients from flowing water into the wetland.

Wetlands originate in regions where rainfall exceeds the potential evapotranspiration remaining a collected water surplus. Environmentally, one-third of the Indian sub-continent comes under this category of wetlands. They are thus very common across the geographical land of the country especially in East & West Coastal regions, Assam, Orissa, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jammu and Kashmir, Eastern Madhya Pradesh, North-Eastern Andhra Pradesh, and Uttarakhand. Gopal (1982) has observed 1193 wetlands comprising a total land area of 3.9 million hectares in 274 districts across India. Directory of Indian Wetlands (1993) records that Indian wetlands cover 58.2 million hectares area of the country. The major types of wetland Zones in India are (DIW, 1993): 1) reservoir, tanks and other water bodies in Deccan peninsula, 2) backwaters and estuaries of the west coast, 3) saline areas of Rann of Kachch, 4) reservoirs and freshwater lakes in Gujarat, Rajasthan & Madhya Pradesh, 5) lagoons, deltas, & salt swamps of the eastern coast, 6) terai swamps, marshes, Chaur and Jheels of Indo-Gangetic plain, 7) Brahmaputra floodplain & marshes/swamps of North-East India, and 8) rivers & lakes of Kashmir and Ladakh.

Study Area

The present study focused on the evaluation of common resource property as a wetland resource in Assam state. Extensive water bodies commonly called ‘beels’ in Assam (Jhingran and Pathak, 1987) which are the key source of fishing for rural poor in a village. 3513 wetlands are covering a total area of 101 232 hectares (Baruah et al, 2000) i.e. approximately 4% of the total floodplain & 1.3% of the total land surface of the State. Moreover, 690 lakes/ponds are covering 15 494 hectares, 861 oxbow lakes/cut-off meanders covering 15 461 hectares, 1126 waterlogged areas occupy 23 436 hectares, 712 swamps and marshes cover an area of 43 434 hectares in the state of Assam. These wetlands are an important resource of economy & nutrition for the human being because they facilitate a habitat for aquatic flora & fauna and birds. Major economic activity in these beels are fishing; vegetables & rice cultivation in the catchment areas during post-monsoon. These beels are highly rich in nutrients and having a high potentiality of production. Jhingran and Pathak (1987) have assessed the potentiality of the production of beels at 1 500 kg/ha/year. However, the potentiality of the production of these beels varies from place to place.

The environmental degradation of these beels can be traced with the influx of water hyacinth in a century ago. The rapid growth of water hyacinth weed hampers the infiltration of sunlight, preventing planktonic growth and facilitates eutrophication by reducing the flow of water currents and dumping debris at the bottommost. The next stage of boosted eutrophication is caused by the construction of dams along the Brahmaputra River which caused the devastating earthquake in 1950. These embankments considerably diminished the sporadic flushing by monsoon water floods. The final stage of wetlands degradation has been caused by human interference such as the rearing of cattle, different kind of agriculture activities and overfishing. These human activities have caused damage and siltation of water quality and microflora.

The irrational application of pesticides in agricultural activities has caused accumulation of deposits by surface water flow, leading biomagnification in these beels. Freshwater living beings like reptiles and numerous other species that were copious in many beels have extinct or greatly endangered. The biodiversity change affects the livelihood and food security of the local population depending on these beels. Evidence on the ecological correlation between biodiversity changes and changes in primary productivity of these beels need to formulate suitable policies for conservation and other ecological initiatives.

Statement of the Problem

Owing to the volume of goods and services provided by wetlands, they have truly been termed as "waterlogged wealth". However, most of the time, adequate attention has not been paid for their management. Wetlands have been considered by most as merely "wasteland" despite their valuable services and considered that their true value can be achieved only after converting to some other use. As a result, encroachment, reclamation, pollution, poaching of aquatic animals and avifauna, etc. have caused great harm to the wetlands. The wetlands in Assam too, are facing similar kinds of problems. Among all the wetlands in Assam, one of the most important is the Deepor Beel, located on the southern boundary of Guwahati city. It is the only Ramsar site in Assam. But being located on the fringe of a rapidly expanding city, the wetland has witnessed severe threat in terms of loss in area, biodiversity and water quality. Dumping of untreated waste, sewage, and construction of new railway trek across the wetland boundary has aggravated the problem only. Hence this study has been undertaken to see the complex relationship of the man environment and consequent anthropogenic impact on the ecosystem.

Deepor Beel Wetland

The Deepor Beel has extended between, $91^{\circ} 37' E$ to $91^{\circ} 40' E$ and $26^{\circ} 5' N$ to $26^{\circ} 9' N$, in the southern part of Brahmaputra River in Kamrup District of Assam. The Deepor Beel wetland is located at an altitude of 53-meter AMSL & covers 4000 hectares. The wetland supports 50 different species of fishes. A study revealed that there are at least 12 lizards, 20 amphibians, 18 snakes, and 6 tortoise species in Deepor Beel (ENVIS Newsletters,2003). This wetland & neighboring forest areas support to the number of land-dwelling and aquatic bird species, most of them are endangered, endemic and threatened. Overall, 202 bird species have been verified, among them 70 are waterfowl. Owing to this rich biodiversity, Deepor Beel has been listed in the Ramsar list as the site no. 1207 in 2002. In addition to it, the core 4.1 sq. km and a total of 10.1 sq. km of the wetland has been demarcated as a bird sanctuary and reserve forest, respectively.

The present study is an attempt to analyze the common property resources and its management of Deepor Beel wetland a Ramsar Site, Assam. The key objective of the study is to look at the wetland as a CPR and to see how they have been utilized and managed. Various published reports, articles, references, as well as satellite imageries and topographical sheets, have been used as a secondary source of data to carry forward this study.

Services and Dependency on Deepor Beel

The Deepor Beel is one of the unique wetlands in the region. It is an abandoned channel of Brahmaputra River. It harbors a rich variety of biodiversity. Though, there is no such study has been done to evaluate the economic value of the goods and services of the wetland. However, reports from many individual studies show that wetland is a treasure house of both direct and indirect value. Being located on the fringe of the city, it serves as one of the most important stormwater reservoirs of Guwahati city. The biological productivity of this natural wetland is exceptionally high. There are several villages on the fringe of Deepor Beel who entirely depend on the fish caught in the Beel for their livelihood. In addition to fish, the wetland also provides a good quantity of grasses which are used as fodder. Water hyacinth, although weeds grow extensively, is also used as manure by the locals. The wetland also helps in maintaining the groundwater table in the surrounding area, otherwise, which has become a major issue of concern in the other part of the Guwahati city. The wetland also plays a crucial role in maintaining a pleasant microclimate in the region.

The wetland provides a good scope for tourism in the region. During winters, a great folk of migratory birds uses to come to this wetland, which attracts huge flux of tourists to the wetland. There is a very good prospect of developing water sports in the wetland, which will further help in the development of tourism and also serve as earning avenue for the people living in the fringe areas.

The wetland produces a very good quantity of "Makhana", which attracts the wild elephants from the adjoining forest to this wetland. Another important service provided by the wetland is the cultivation of winter paddy on the wetland soil. The rich organic soil has attracted the agricultural community to go for winter rice cultivation. Thus it can be concluded that the Deepor Beel wetland serves as a rich source of goods and services to the people living on the fringe of it. Hence, there is an urgent need for sustainable management of the wetland so that the benefits of the wetland can be enjoyed without hampering the sustainability of the ecosystem (Bhuyan B., 2009).

Management of the Wetland

Traditionally, the wetlands in Assam has been managed by the local communities and regarded as CPR. The local people formulated their own rules and regulation for the effective management of these resources. One example can be cited here, in the entire region, the people restrain their fishing activity during the brooding period so that the stock of fish increases in due time. Also, ethics were followed not to catch the juveniles. All these ethics were followed so that sustainability remains over time. However, over time and with the mounting population pressure on the resources, such tradition is losing their ground. Moreover, the state has taken the exclusive right of these CPR and formulated many regulations for the management, often keeping the locals out of these CPR. Earlier, the wetlands in Assam were managed by the communities living on the fringe. But gradually, the ownership rights of these wetlands have been transferred. Today, most of the wetland comes under the revenue department (Settlement) of the state.

Several wetlands have been given to Assam Fisheries Development Corporation (AFDC) for their maintenance in 1977. The AFDC and Revenue Department has leased out these wetlands for a period of five years to generate revenue. However, the interest of local fishing communities i.e. Koibortta's has been neglected completely under this system. The system permits only the rich auction-goers to get the leases. Moreover, the advertising of the catch is managed by the lessee. The fishermen are not permitted to trade their portion in the market but they have to sell back to the lessee at very low prices fixed by the lessee themselves. Generally, the lessees have only a motive to maximize their profit due to the fixed period of these leases. On the other hand, the lessee fish out the complete stock of fishes from the wetlands. Thus, it is clear that these are a violation of provisions of the Indian Fisheries Act 1897, legislated for the conservation and protection of fish biota (Baruah et al, 2000).

The management of Deepor Beel is perhaps one of the most complexes in the entire country. The wetland comes under three different departments simultaneously, the Forest Department, Revenue Department, and the AFDC. Traditionally, the Koibortta people on the fringe villages earned their livelihood by carrying out fishing in the wetland. However, only controlled fishing is allowed at present, the fishers are issued a license by the concerned department to fish in the beel. This too is a clear case of restricting the poor from the use of CPRs.

Dynamics of Deepor Beel Wetland

An attempt has been undertaken to carry out the Spatio-temporal analysis of Deepor Beel using satellite imageries to monitor the change during the period from 1977 to 2006. For this purpose, satellite imageries from the USGS site have been downloaded, processed and analyzed using ArcMap 10.2.2 and ERDAS IMAGINE 2014 software. Various images and they're brief have been tabulated as below:

Serial No.	Sensor	Resolution (m)	Date of Acquisition
1.	MSS	70	28-02-1977
2.	LandSat TM	30	26-11-1991
3.	LandSat ETM+	30	17-02-2002
4.	LandSat ETM+	30	26-10-2006

The study area of Deepor Beel comprises of the watershed boundary of the wetland, prepared from the Survey of India Topographical Sheets no. 78 N/12 and 78 N/16. It covers an approximate area of 211 sq. km.

Supervised Classification of the satellite images has been carried out using ERDAS IMAGINE 14, after detailed ground-truthing. Seven Land Use Land Cover categories are derived based on image processing throughout a period of study for Deepor Beel catchment (Table 2) and (Fig. 2).

Land Cover Category/Area (ha)	1977	1991	2002	2006
Dense Forest	10209.0078	10241.47	10710.54	11176.47
Open Forest	4549.5747	4039.72	4173.3	3925.98
Agriculture Land	835.3179	491.33	1468.35	332.82
Fallow Land	2456.8938	1981.23	1297.62	2240.37
Water Spread Area	475.9785	687.05	485.73	450.54
Swampy Land	1849.3308	2528.38	1418.94	1045.62
Built-Up Land	866.87	1273.79	1688.49	2071.17
Total	21242.97	21242.97	21242.97	21242.97

Analysis of the data thus obtained shows that there is a steady decline in water spread area, basically the wetland areas. Here to be noted is that the water spread area refers to the area of the wetland, still retaining water during the lean period, as satellite images of the study area are all from the cloud-free period of the year which corresponds to late autumn and early spring season. Data clearly shows that there is a very steep rise in built-up lands, basically the urban structures, including roads and all impervious concrete structures (Fig.1). At the same time, there is a sharp decline in the swampy lands.

Land Cover Category/pc change in the area	(1977-1991)	(1991-2002)	(2002-2006)	(1977-2006)
Dense Forest	0.32	4.58	4.35	9.48
Open Forest	-11.21	3.31	-5.93	-13.71
Agriculture Land	-41.18	198.85	-77.33	-60.16
Fallow Land	-19.36	-34.50	72.65	-8.81
Water Spread Area	44.34	-29.30	-7.24	-5.34
Swampy Land	36.72	-43.88	-26.31	-43.46
Built-Up Land	46.94	32.56	22.66	138.93

It has been observed that the wetland area has registered more than 5% loss over the period 1977-2006 while urban expansion registers a whopping almost 140% over the same period (Table 3). On the other hand, swampy areas have declined by nearly 43% during this period. Most of the areas under decline have primarily been transformed to build up areas (Bhuyan B., 2019).

Fig. 1: Areas under different Land Use Land Cover Category

Fig. 2: Land Use land Cover Map of Deepor Beel Catchment

Future Scope of Study

From the ongoing discussion, it has become clear that the wetlands have proved to be very rich CPRs, but are under a very bad management system. There must be some specific management plan which will incorporate the traditional knowledge with the latest technological inputs and most importantly, include the local people

as a part of such a sustainable management system. Then only, the true use of the wetlands will be achieved. There is also a need to carry out extensive study for the economic evaluation of the wetlands so that true recognition can be given to the wetlands for their invaluable direct and indirect services. A Spatio-temporal study using geospatial technologies will be very much helpful for monitoring any change in the wetland area. It is also possible to predict future change and the health of the wetlands using such technological advantages. Thus a holistic approach involving various stockholders will enable proper sustainable management of our rich wetlands.

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